

Condensation and Oxidation Reactions of 5-Pyrazolones

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A mechanism has been suggested for the condensation of benzaldehyde with 5-pyrazolone. An explanation has been given for the formation of arylidene monopyrazolone compounds from dimethylaminobenzaldehyde and cinnamaldehyde. Cyclopropane compounds have been formed by the oxidation of 4,4'-benzylidene-bis-(5-pyrazolone) compounds with iodine. Original compounds have been obtained by the opening up of cyclopropane rings.

It has been concluded¹ from study of reaction of aromatic aldehydes with compounds having reactive methylene groups, that formation of benzylidene bis-compounds involve an intermediate of the type $R-CH = C \begin{matrix} \swarrow^x \\ \searrow^y \end{matrix}$ which undergoes Michael condensation with a second molecule of the reactive methylene compound. It has been reported earlier² that benzaldehyde reacts with 3-methyl-1-phenyl-5-pyrazolone in acetic acid solution to produce two products, compounds I and II, whereas reaction of the parent pyrazolone with benzaldehyde in ethanolic medium in the presence of piperidine produces only product III.

The formation of 4,4'-benzylidene-bis-(3-methyl-1-phenyl-5-pyrazolone) can thus take place in the manner : as shown in the structure (next page).

It has been found that substituted benzaldehydes having chloro, nitro, methoxyl, and hydroxyl groups in different positions condensed with 5-pyrazolone in the presence of piperidine to produce the corresponding arylidene bis-compounds³. However, *p*-dimethylaminobenzaldehyde and cinnamaldehyde have been found to condense with the 5-pyrazolone in the presence of piperidine to produce arylidene mono-pyrazolone compounds; the two aldehydes condense with 5-isooxazolone in the presence of piperidine to produce only

1. I. L. Finar, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1961, 674.
2. A. S. Mitra and M. K. Rout, *Jour. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1961, **38**, 893.
3. A. S. Mitra and M. K. Rout, *Jour. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1963, **40**, 833.

4-arylidene-5-isooxazolone compounds. Donleavy and Gilbert⁴ have reported that 4-arylidene-5-isooxazolone is converted to 4,4'-arylidene-bis-(5-isooxazolone) by heating with

aqueous sodium carbonate solution. 4-(*p*-dimethylamino-benzylidene)-3-methyl-5-isooxazolone has been treated with aqueous sodium carbonate solution and unconverted starting material was obtained.

The failure of the compounds to produce bis-compounds by undergoing Michael addition is due to the migration of the positive charge from the carbon, which is in β -position to the carbonyl group of the arylidene mono-pyrazolone compound, to the phenyl ring of the aldehyde residue over the conjugated carbon chain by a process involving both allylic and benzylic shifts.

It has been noted that the 5-pyrazolone ring system is resistant to acids and alkalis. One recorded instance of the opening up of the 5-pyrazolone ring is found⁵. Perroncita⁵ noted that 3-methyl-1-phenyl-5-pyrazolone is oxidised by arsenic acid in acetic acid medium or by potassium permanganate in hydrochloric acid, to 4-benzeneazo-3-methyl-1-phenyl-5-pyrazolone and some other products.

In this investigation attempt has been made to open up the pyrazolone ring by oxidation with iodine in alkaline solution. A solid crystalline product has been obtained by oxidation of 4,4'-benzylidene-bis-(3-methyl-1-phenyl-5-pyrazolone) with iodine in alkaline solution. One possible course of the reaction shown below leads to a product, A, of β -diketone structure.

The product obtained did not give any phenylhydrazone or 2,4-dinitrophenylhydrazone. It gave no colouration with alcoholic ferric chloride and was not soluble in aqueous sodium hydroxide. So the product of oxidation can not be a β -diketone.

On Michael condensation of sodium salt of 4-bromo-5-pyrazolone with 4-alkylidene-5-pyrazolone an adduct is obtained which splits off sodium bromide to yield cyclopropane⁶. The properties of the iodine oxidation compound prepared in this study are those expected of a cyclopropane type compound.

5. I. Perroncita, *Gazz. Chem. Ital. Chem.*, 1935, 1936 through *British. Chem. Abstr. A.* 1936, 614.
6. Gummel Westoo, *Acta. Chem. Scand.*, 1957, 11, 1290.

The structure B is assigned to the iodine oxidation product. The I.R. absorption spectrum of the compound shows carbonyl absorption peak at 1720 cm^{-1} . This frequency is close to the carbonyl frequency 1712 cm^{-1} of unenolisable 5-pyrazolone compound 4,4'-benzylidene-bis-(3,4-dimethyl-1-phenyl-5-pyrazolone)⁷.

EXPERIMENTAL

Michael addition of 5-pyrazolone to 4-arylidene-5-pyrazolone: 4-benzylidene-3-methyl-1-phenyl-5-pyrazolone (2.6 g.) was dissolved in absolute alcohol (30 ml). The solution was placed on the water-bath and a solution of 3-methyl-1-phenyl-5-pyrazolone (1.7 g) in 10% sodium hydroxide solution (4 ml.) was added. The mixture got decolourised within half a minute, and the solution was refluxed for half an hour. Heating was continued after removing the reflux condenser to remove the alcohol. The solution was cooled and acidified with dilute acetic acid. A yellow solid separated out. This was filtered off and crystallised from methyl alcohol, found m.p. $161\text{--}163^\circ$. A mixed melting point determination with the carbonyl form of 4,4'-benzylidene-bis-(3-methyl-1-phenyl-5-pyrazolone) did not depress the melting point.

Michael addition of 5-pyrazolone to 4-(*p*-dimethylaminobenzylidene)-3-methyl-1-phenyl-5-pyrazolone was attempted. 4-(*p*-dimethylaminobenzylidene)-3-methyl-1-phenyl-5-pyrazolone (3.0 g.) was dissolved in hot absolute alcohol (40 ml.). 3-methyl-1-phenyl-5-pyrazolone (1.7 g.) was dissolved in 10% aqueous sodium hydroxide solution (4 ml.). The two solutions were mixed and then refluxed for one hour. Then the product was worked up. After recrystallisation from methyl alcohol the product melted at 197° . The mixed melting point with 4-(*p*-dimethylaminobenzylidene)-3-methyl-1-phenyl-5-pyrazolone did not show any depression.

Condensation of cinnamaldehyde with 3-methyl-1-phenyl-5-pyrazolone: 3-methyl-1-phenyl-5-pyrazolone (1.2 g.) was dissolved in minimum volume of glacial acetic acid. Freshly distilled cinnamaldehyde (0.9 g.) was added. The mixture was allowed to stand for 12 hr. at room temperature. Red precipitate separated out, m.p. 152° (Found: C, 78.89; H, 5.31; $\text{C}_{19}\text{H}_{16}\text{ON}_2$, requires: C, 79.11; H, 5.55%).

3-methyl-1-phenyl-5-pyrazolone (1.2 g.) was next dissolved in minimum volume of absolute alcohol at room temperature, freshly distilled cinnamaldehyde (0.9 g.) and piperidine (10 drops) were added. The mixture was left at room temperature for 12 hr. A red crystalline product separated out. It was filtered off and washed with a little absolute alcohol, found m.p. 152° . A mixed melting point of the above two cinnamaldehyde condensation products was also found to be 152° .

Oxidation of 4,4'-benzylidene-bis-(3-methyl-1-phenyl-5-pyrazolone) with iodine: 4,4'-benzylidene-bis-(3-methyl-1-phenyl-5-pyrazolone), carbonyl form, m.p. $161\text{--}63^\circ$, (5 g.), was dissolved in a 20% sodium hydroxide solution (30 ml.) at the room temperature. A strong aqueous solution of iodine in potassium iodide was prepared. The iodine solution was added dropwise to the alkaline solution of the pyrazolone compound with continuous stirring till complete precipitation. This was allowed to stand for 2 hr. and was then

7. A. S. Mitra and M. K. Rout, *Jour. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1963, **40**, 993.

filtered. The residue was washed with sulphurous acid solution (*i.e.*, sodium bisulphite in dilute sulphuric acid) to remove free iodine. The product melted at 166° after crystallisation from acetone. This compound showed strong I.R. absorption peaks at 1720 cm⁻¹, 1325 cm⁻¹, 1294 cm⁻¹, 1278 cm⁻¹, 758 cm⁻¹, 740 cm⁻¹ and 692 cm⁻¹.

The above iodine oxidation product (0.58 g.), zinc dust (2 g.), and glacial acetic acid (10 ml.) were taken in a conical flask and heated on a boiling water bath for 4 hr. The mixture was filtered hot. The filtrate was cooled and then diluted with drops of water till turbidity appeared. Again it was heated till clear. On cooling a solid crystalline product was obtained, m.p. 161-63°. Mixed melting point with the carbonyl form of 4,4'-benzylidene-bis-(3-methyl-1-phenyl-5-pyrazolone) did not depress the melting point. The melting points and analytical values of cyclopropane compounds prepared are given below in tabular form.

R	M.pt.	% C		% H	
		Expected	Found	Expected	Found
	166°	74.46	74.01	5.06	4.87
Cl	>270°	69.23	68.97	4.48	4.51
	175°	67.68	67.61	4.38	4.40

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